

1 **The dendritic cell transcriptome following HIV-1 infection.**

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7 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in monocyte-derived dendritic cells following *in vitro*
8 challenge with HIV-1 to model HIV-1 infection in the dendritic cell. Cells manifested altered cell cycle
9 characterized by activation of *G0S2*. Cells activated immune receptors *Fcrlb* and *Lrrc32* in response to
10 HIV-1 infection, as well as the interferon-stimulated gene *Ifitm3*. We describe silencing of the adenylate
11 cyclase component *ADCY1* during DC cell HIV-1 infection. Monocyte-derived dendritic cells challenged
12 with HIV-1 exhibited activation of non-classical cell death program components marked by *Gpx3* induction.

13 Citations

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